

BLUE GENES RETREAT

DAY 1 / 3

08h30	Gathering at the ICM and Departure to Cala Canyelles
10h30	Welcoming, Group cohesion, and Initial conversations to foster synergies
12h25	Prioritizing synergies, forming action-research groups, and self-organization tips for accommodations
13h45	Lunch break @ Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles
16h00	Action scenarios, priorities and timeline development
18h00	Event UN Ocean Decade: Creative planning session
19h15	Wrap-up. Mauricio's poem & logistics reminder
20h	Walk to accommodations
20h15	Dinner preparation

Thursday, February 15, 2024

Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC) Pg. Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37
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BLUE GENES RETREAT

DAY 2/3

09h30	Morning cohesion: Movement exploration with the sea by Mauricio
10h00	Shaping the UN event: Defining activities and organizational structure
12h00	Assigning roles and group collaboration for UN event preparation
14h00	Lunch break @ Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles
16h00	Parallel workshop space - Participants: Eulàlia, Eva, Ladislav, Diego / Possible extra session for UN event
18h15	Community future, next steps, and timelines
19h30	Wrap-up
20h	Walk to accommodations
20h15	Dinner preparation

Friday, February 16, 2024

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DAY 3/3

09h30	Participant opening: Soundscape active listening by Ilaria
10h00	Exchange space continues: Group art activity (Ilaria, Ladislav, Emily)
11h30	Greetings, feedback and closure
13h00	Lunch break @ Club Nàutic Cala Canyelles
15h00	Return journey!

Saturday, February 17, 2024

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